

IMAGE, MARKETING MIX SERVICE USE INNOVATION, TRUST, SERVICE DECISION AFFECTING LOYALTY OF TUTORING INSTITUTES IN PHUKET PROVINCE

VIPARANEE KAEWSAI ¹, JONGDEE PHUSALUX ², TANAPOL KORTANA³,
CHOMPOO SAISAMA ⁴ and PEERAWEE TEPPRATUANGTIP ⁵

^{1,2,3,4,5} Suan Sunadha Rajabhat University, Thailand.

E-Mail: ¹s61484945039@ssru.ac.th, ²jongdee.ph@ssru.ac.th, ³tanapol.ko@ssru.ac.th, ⁴chompo.sa@ssru.ac.th, ⁵peerawee.te@ssru.ac.th

Abstract

The competitive entrance examinations for state universities and popular fields of study, especially in science and social sciences, have resulted in intense competition, stress, and many disappointed students. Thus, tutoring schools or institutions need to understand additional lessons to learn techniques and methods to solve problems more easily and quickly to help students enter their desired educational institutions. This research aims to: 1) Study the levels of image, marketing mix, service innovation, trust, and decision-making in service usage affecting customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province. 2) Examine the influence of variables such as image, marketing mix, service innovation, trust, and decision-making in service usage on customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province. 3) Develop a model for customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in the future in Phuket Province. This research employs a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative research. For the quantitative part, the sample consists of 500 students and parents from secondary schools under the Ministry of Education who use tutoring services in Phuket Province. The sample size was determined using a criterion of 20 times the observed variables and was selected using a multi-stage sampling method. The study used questionnaires for data collection and analyzed the data using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). In-depth interviews were conducted with 20 participants, including 10 tutoring institution operators and 10 experts in the tutoring business in Phuket Province. The research findings revealed that: 1) The levels of image, marketing mix, service innovation, trust, and decision-making in service usage had a high impact on customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket. 2) These factors significantly affected customer loyalty at a statistically significant level of 0.05. 3) The customer loyalty model developed by the researcher for tutoring institutions in Phuket is called the ISMTD-CLTP Model (I = Image, D = Decision-making, S = Service Innovation, T = Trust, M = Marketing Mix, CLTP = Customer Loyalty of Tutoring Institutions in Phuket Province). Additionally, the qualitative findings suggest that operators should adopt new digital technologies and innovations, enhance modern communication channels, offer tutoring services through social networks, and provide online learning to improve customer satisfaction and foster loyalty in the future.

Keywords: Image, Trust of Tutoring Institutions, Decision-Making in Service Usage, Phuket Province.

INTRODUCTION

Education in Thai society is highly competitive, but the educational standards of each school vary, including the slow development of teaching styles. As a result, the measurement of learning outcomes is not up to the standards set by the Ministry of Education. This situation creates a value among students who seek additional classes outside of regular school hours. These additional classes are usually taken at tutoring institutes to gain a better understanding of lessons, learn techniques, and practice question formats to answer more easily and quickly.

Therefore, tutoring schools have become very important in the Thai education system, helping students achieve success as measured by scores in various subjects according to the Ministry of Education and university requirements. Tutoring schools are thus linked to the selection process for studying at desired universities because of the competitive entrance exams to reputable institutions. Due to the limited number of accepted students compared to the large number of applicants, regular school education alone is often insufficient. Students must therefore strive to gain additional knowledge from tutoring schools to score better than others in exams. Tutoring for secondary school students is thus very necessary.

The competitive examination conditions for entering public universities and popular market subjects are equally fierce. Income varies greatly between occupations, especially between science and social science careers. This disparity makes many social science faculties unpopular, while faculties such as engineering, medicine, commerce, and accounting attract many applicants. This intense competition leads to disappointment for many students (Arquero, Fernández-Polvillo, & Jiménez-Cardoso, 2024). The disparity in the quality of education and career opportunities between those who have and those who have not attended university causes the demand for university admission to continue to increase. Budget constraints necessitate the selection examination, which highlights educational inequality more clearly. Data from the Kasikorn Research Center states that in 2018, parents with children studying from kindergarten to high school spent a total of 27,500 million baht on education, an increase of 9.0 percent compared to the first school term in 2017

Therefore, tutoring institutions or tutoring schools in Phuket need to adapt to become an important option. People who come to use the service or customers include stakeholders and have the potential to be active under rapid change. This necessitates fixing the management system that lacks clarity, as it leads to inefficiency when linking tutoring institutions in the region (Aranzabal, Epelde, & Artetxe, 2022). The lack of clarity impacts the decision to choose to study at a tutoring institution, which in turn affects the institution's operational efficiency and decision-making (Aydiner, Tatoglu, Bayraktar, & Zaim, 2019).

Improving these aspects will bring benefits according to the important goals of the institution. Effective management in tutoring influences the decision to choose a tutoring institution and helps increase competitive potential (Bazińska, Korpalski, & Szpindler, 2019). Therefore, the researcher is interested in studying the image and marketing mix, service innovation, trust, and service use decisions that affect the loyalty of tutoring institution users in Phuket province. The image of the tutoring institution is supported by factors such as its reputation and experience, a well-designed website, reliable past performance, and the number of students who have passed the university entrance exam.

Additionally, the location of the tutoring institute should be easily accessible, situated in a community area, and provide facilities such as shops, restaurants, ample parking, or comfortable waiting areas for parents. The number of students in each classroom should be appropriate and not too crowded. Personnel should be attentive, smiling, and friendly (Baeten & Simons, 2014). Teachers and staff of the tutoring institute need to have an understanding of children's human relations and provide quick and friendly service. Regarding the marketing

mix of tutoring institutes, supporting factors include having courses with outstanding and unique content, providing worthwhile and suitable textbooks, and offering flexible class schedules to give students more study options. Tuition fees should be reduced under appropriate conditions, and students should be able to retake classes at no additional cost if they do not understand the material (Ginting, Mahiranissa, Bektı, & Febriansyah, 2020).

Satisfaction with the services of tutoring institutions includes factors such as providing services on a first-come, first-served basis, having staff to assist at every step of the operation process, presenting interesting content on the website, ensuring security, and specifying rights to access user data (Gowri Shankar & Seow, 2010). Innovation in tutoring institutions is supported by the use of teaching techniques that stimulate learning, enhance culture, and create collaborative learning networks (Abele et al., 2017). These factors affect the decision to choose to study at tutoring institutions in Phuket Province. This research aims to further develop and improve the management process for efficiency in Phuket Province.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scope of research

1. Demographic scope and sample group

The population used in this research consists of students and parents from secondary schools under the Ministry of Education who are users of tutoring institutes in Phuket Province. The total population is 2,235 people (Ministry of Education, 2017).

The quantitative sample was obtained by determining the sample size based on an estimated ratio of observation variables, with a proportion of 1 to 20. In this research, there were 25 observed variables. Therefore, the researcher set the sample size at 500 people, using multistage random sampling from students and parents from secondary schools under the Ministry of Education who use tutoring institutes in Phuket Province.

The qualitative sample group was gathered through in-depth interviews with 20 experts who have expertise and a thorough understanding of the effectiveness of the management of tutoring institutions in Phuket. This sample was selected by purposive sampling and the data was analyzed using content analysis.

2. Scope of variables

The researcher summarized the study variables into two categories: endogenous and exogenous latent variables. The endogenous latent variables include trust, decision to use services, and loyalty of service users.

Trust consists of administration and teaching and learning. The decision to use services involves perception, search, evaluation, and decision making. Loyalty includes positive attitude, repeat service use, liking, and telling others. The exogenous latent variables comprise image, marketing mix, and service innovation. Image includes location, teaching personnel, and teaching curriculum.

The marketing mix covers the product, price, personnel, promotion, distribution channel, process, and physical characteristics. Service innovation encompasses teaching media innovation, knowledge innovation, learning atmosphere, teaching achievement, and measurement.

Latent Variable	Observation Variable
Image (IMAGE)	Location (LOCA)
	Teaching Personnel (TEAC)
	Course (COUR)
Marketing mix (MARK)	Products (PROD)
	Price (PRIC)
	Personnel (PERS)
	Promotion of Marketing (PROM)
	Distribution Channel (DIST)
	Process (PROC)
	Physical Characteristics (PHYS)
Innovation in Service (INNO)	Instructional Media Innovation (MEDI)
	Knowledge Innovation (KNOW)
	Innovative Learning Environment (CLIM)
	Teaching Achievement (ACHI)
	Measurement (EVAL)
	Administration (MANA)
	Organize Teaching and Learning (EDUC)
trust (TRUS) Deciding to use services (DECI)	Knowing the Problem (PROB)
	Searching for Information (SEAR)
	Evaluate Options (OPTI)
	Decision Making (DMAK)
	Positive Attitude (ATTI)

3. Content scope

In this research, the content consists of Image, Marketing mix, Trust, Service innovation, deciding to use services, Loyalty of service users

RESEARCH RESULT

Details of the presentation of data analysis results are as follows:

Part 1- Results of the general information study of the sample group.

The researcher collected data from a sample group of 500 students and parents who used the services of tutoring institutions in Phuket province. The details are as follows: The majority of the sample were female, with 333 people, accounting for 66.60 percent, and males, with 167 people, accounting for 33.40 percent.

There were 160 people aged 20 - 30 years, accounting for 32.00 percent, followed by 142 people aged 31 - 40 years, representing 28.40 percent, 69 people aged 41 - 50 years, representing 13.80 percent, 54 people under 20 years, representing 10.80 percent, and 54

people aged 51 - 60 years, representing 10.80 percent. The lowest group was those over 60 years old, with 21 people, accounting for 4.20 percent. Regarding education level, 260 people had below a bachelor's degree, accounting for 52.00 percent, followed by 148 people with a bachelor's degree, accounting for 29.60 percent. The lowest group had above a bachelor's degree, with 92 people, accounting for 18.40 percent.

The highest monthly income group was those earning between 30,001 - 50,000 baht, with 192 people, representing 38.40 percent, followed by those earning 50,001 - 100,000 baht, with 113 people, representing 22.60 percent. There were 73 people earning 20,000 - 30,000 baht, representing 14.60 percent, and 71 people earning less than 20,000 baht, representing 14.20 percent. The lowest group had an income of more than 100,000 baht, with 51 people, accounting for 10.20 percent.

It was found that most of the people who used tutoring institute services were parents, with 304 people, representing 60.80 percent, and 196 people were self-learners, representing 39.20 percent. Regarding the duration of tutoring, the highest number of people, 142, had been tutored for more than 1 year to 2 years, representing 28.40 percent, followed by 140 people who had been tutored for 6 months to 1 year, accounting for 28.00 percent.

There were 102 people who had been tutored for more than 2 years to 3 years, accounting for 20.40 percent, and 76 people who had been tutored for less than 6 months, accounting for 15.20 percent. The lowest group had been tutored for more than 3 years, with 40 people, accounting for 8.00 percent.

Table 1: Mean Standard Deviation and interpretation of variables, image, and marketing mix. Service innovation, trust, service use decisions that affect the loyalty of tutoring institution users in Phuket province (n=500)

variable	\bar{X}	SD	meaning
Image (IMAG)	4.18	0.72	a lot
Marketing mix (MARK)	3.83	0.57	a lot
Innovation in service (INNO)	4.07	0.78	a lot
Trust (TRUS)	4.04	0.70	a lot
Loyalty of service users (LOYA)	4.10	0.68	a lot

The image (IMAG) was found to be at a high level, equal to 4.10. When considering each aspect, it was found that the Location aspect (LOCA), teaching personnel aspect (TEAC), and curriculum aspect (COUR) are all at a high level, ranging between 4.15 and 4.22. The marketing mix (MARK) is at a high level, equal to 3.83.

When considering each aspect, it was found that the Product side (PRD), price side (PRIC), personnel side (PERS), marketing promotion side (PROM), distribution channel side (DIST), process side (PROC), and physical characteristics side (PHYS) are all at a high level, ranging between 3.69 and 4.04.

Service innovation (INNO) is at a high level, equal to 4.07. When considering each aspect, it was found that teaching media innovation (MEDI), knowledge innovation (KNOW), learning atmosphere innovation (CLIM), teaching achievement (ACHI), and measurement (EVAL) are

all at a high level, ranging between 4.03 and 4.11. Trust (TRUS) is at a high level, equal to 4.04. When considering each aspect, it was found that the administrative aspect (MANA) and teaching and learning aspect (EDUC) are all at a high level, ranging between 4.02 and 4.05. The decision to use services (DECI) was at a high level, equal to 4.09.

When considering each aspect, it was found that problem knowledge (PROB), information search (SEAR), alternative evaluation (OPTI), and decision-making (DMAK) are all at a high level, ranging between 4.06 and 4.22. Loyalty of service users (LOYA) is at a high level, equal to 4.10. When considering each aspect, it was found that positive attitude (ATTI), repeat service use (REPU), increased liking (PERF), and word of mouth or recommending others (WORD) are all at a high level, ranging between 4.04 and 4.13.

Part 2- Results of the study of the influence of image marketing mix Service innovation, trust, service use decisions that affect the loyalty of tutoring institution users in Phuket province.

Data analysis was performed using structural equation modeling techniques (SEM) and LISREL Version 8.72. The researcher has checked the basic statistical assumptions, and the results of the data analysis according to the research objectives are as follows:

1. Normal distribution of empirical variables (n=500).
2. Correlation coefficient between pairs of empirical variables used in the study in the model (Observation Correlation Test) (n=500).
3. Overall relationships among the empirical variables studied in the structural equation model (n=500).
4. Measurement model that is studied in the model (n=500) and then proceeds to analyze the data to check.
5. Results of the analysis of the structural equation model according to the hypothesis (Hypothesis Model) (n=500).
6. Results of the analysis of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjusted Model) (n=500).
7. Equations of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjusted Model) (n=500).

Results of the analysis of the structural equation model according to the hypothesis (Hypothesis Model)

Conduct a check on the harmony of the Hypothesis Model with the empirical data. With the LISREL package, considering the harmony index value, it was found that the hypothetical model was not yet in harmony with the empirical data. Which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 1645.88$, $df = 240$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 7.69$, $RMSEA = .126$, $RMR = .048$, $SRMR = .11$, $CFI = .95$, $GFI = .78$, $AGFI = .80$, $CN = 68.65$

It was found that $\chi^2 = 1645.88$, $df = 240$ $p\text{-value} = .00000$ has not yet passed the criteria because it is still statistically significant. $\chi^2 / df = 6.86$ has not yet passed the criteria Because it still

has a value greater than 2.00, RMSEA = .126 has not yet passed the criteria. Because it still has a value greater than .05, RMR = .048 passes the criteria because it has a value less than .05. SRMR = .11 does not pass the criteria because it has a value greater than .05. CFI = .95 passes the criteria because it has a value greater than .90. GFI = .78 did not meet the criteria because it is less than .90. AGFI = .80 did not meet the criteria because it has a value less than .90. CN = 68.65 did not meet the criteria because it has a value less than 200.00.

Such results shows that The Hypothesis Model is not as harmonious with the empirical data as it should be. Because the harmony index values, namely χ^2 , χ^2 / df , RMSEA, SRMR, GFI, AGFI, and CN have not yet met the specified criteria (Abraham, Ali, Andangsari, & Hartanti, 2020) The researcher lacks confidence in estimating various parameters (Parameter Estimation) within the model as per the hypothesis (Hypothesis Model). Therefore, the researcher needs to modify the model (Modification Model) to better align with empirical data.

This involves allowing for variance in the standard error (θ) of the empirical variables in some relationship couples. Consideration will be given to the appropriateness and feasibility of concepts and theories, along with related research findings, to discuss the results of these model modifications. Only when the adjusted model (Adjust Model) aligns with empirical data will the path relationships in the model be thoroughly examined.

Results of the analysis of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjust Model).

The researcher adjusted the hypothetical model to better fit empirical data by allowing the variances of the standard errors (θ) of certain pairs of empirical variables to be correlated. There were 30 pairs in total (degrees of freedom for the Hypothesis Model = 240, degrees of freedom for the Adjusted Model = 210).

The adjusted model (Adjusted Model) was found to be in good harmony with the empirical data, as indicated by the following fit indices: $\chi^2 = 405.50$, $df = 210$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2/df = 1.93$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .043, SRMR = .049, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, and CN = 215.85. The harmony index test found that $\chi^2 = 405.5$, $df = 210$, and $p\text{-value} = .00000$, which did not meet the criteria for statistical significance ($p\text{-value} > .05$) (Alotaibi & Alotaibi, 2021).

However, considering χ^2 / df , which was 1.93, it passed the specified criteria (Cervin, Veas, Piqueras, & Martinez-Gonzalez, 2022). RMSEA = .048 also passed (MacCallum et al., 1996), as did RMR = .043 (Arcolin, Godi, & Corna, 2022), and SRMR = .049 (Al Zarooni, Awad, & Alzaatreh, 2022), all being less than .05. CFI = .98, GFI = .94, and AGFI = .91 passed because they were greater than .90 (Wood et al., 2016), while CN = 215.85 passed the criteria (> 200.00) (Jeong, Kim, & Kim, 2021).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the adjusted structural equation model is consistent with the empirical data, and the parameter estimation in such models is acceptable. The results of the analysis are as follows:

Table 2: Results of comparing the calculated statistics with the criteria. To check the consistency with the empirical data of the adjusted structural equation model (Adjust Model).

list of criteria	Specified criteria	Model statistics	consideration
Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square Statistics (χ^2)	P-value greater than or equal to .05	$\chi^2 = 405.50$ df = 210 p-value = .00000	Didn't pass
Relative χ^2 (χ^2 / df)	(Cervin et al., 2022)	1.95	pass
Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Less than or equal to 2.00	.048	pass
Root Mean Squared Residuals (RMR)	(Al Zarooni et al., 2022)	.043	pass
Standardized Root Mean Squared Residual (SRMR)	Less than or equal to .05	.049	pass
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	(Wood et al., 2016)	.98	pass
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	Less than or equal to .05	.94	pass
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	(Wood et al., 2016)	.91	pass
Critical N (CN)	Less than or equal to .05	215.85	pass

That index of the structural equation model that has been adjusted. Harmonious with empirical data which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 405.50$, df = 210, p-value = .00000, $\chi^2 / df = 1.93$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .043, SRMR = .049, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 215.85 from the said harmony index value. Therefore, it can be concluded that the structural equation model that is adjusted (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data. And the estimation of parameters in such models is therefore acceptable.

Table 3: results of estimating the parameters of the Direct Effect coefficient, (Indirect Effect) and (Total Effect) from the modified equation model (n=500)

Dependent variable	R ²	Influence	Variables				
			Image (IMAG)	Marketing mix (MARK)	Innovation in service (INNO)	Trust (TRUS)	Deciding to use services (DECI)
Trust (TRUS)	.74	DE	.78*(10.52)	.54*(9.53)	.48*(8.82)	-	-
		IE	-	-	-	-	-
		TE	.78*(10.52)	.54*(9.53)	.48*(8.82)	-	-
Deciding to use services (DECI)	.51	DE	-	.72*(15.18)	.42*(11.97)	-	-
		IE	-	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	.72*(15.18)	.42*(11.97)	-	-
Loyalty of service users (LOYA)	.58	DE	-	.31*(9.05)	.41*(9.11)	.71*(9.35)	.67*(10.53)
		IE	-	.52*(8.48)	.40*(8.46)	-	-
		TE	-	.83*(8.75)	.81*(12.10)	.71*(9.35)	.67*(10.53)

$\chi^2 = 405.50$, df = 210, p-value = .00000, $\chi^2 / df = 1.93$, RMSEA = .048, RMR = .043, SRMR = .049, CFI = .98, GFI = .94, AGFI = .91, CN = 215.85

* Statistically significant at the .05 level.

It was found that the structural equation model influenced image. Marketing mix Service innovation, trust and decision to use services that affects the loyalty of users of tutoring institutions in Phuket province. The adjustment model (Adjust Model) is in harmony with the empirical data at an acceptable level. Which is considered from the Harmony Index (Fit Index) as follows: $\chi^2 = 405.50$, $df = 210$, $p\text{-value} = .00000$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.93$, $RMSEA = .048$, $RMR = .043$, $SRMR = .049$, $CFI = .98$, $GFI = .94$, $AGFI = .91$, $CN = 215.85$. The estimation was found in the structural equation model as follows.

- 1) The marketing mix (MARK) has a direct influence on trust (TRUS) with an influence coefficient equal to $.54*(9.53)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, in line with hypothesis 1. Markets have a direct, positive influence on trust.
- 2) The marketing mix (MARK) has a direct influence on Loyalty of service users (LOYA) The influence coefficient is equal to $.31*(9.05)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, according to hypothesis 2. The marketing mix has a positive direct influence on the loyalty of service users.
- 3) The marketing mix (MARK) has a direct influence on Decision to use services (DECI) with a coefficient of influence equal to $.72*(15.18)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level is in line with hypothesis 3. The marketing mix has a positive direct influence on the decision to use services.
- 4) Image (IMAG) has a direct influence on trust (TRUS) with a coefficient of influence equal to $.78*(10.52)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, according to hypothesis 4. Image has a direct influence on trust (TRUS). Positive for trust
- 5) Service innovation (INNO) has a direct influence on trust (TRUS) with a coefficient of influence equal to $.48*(8.82)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, in line with hypothesis 5. Service innovation Service has a direct, positive influence on trust.
- 6) Service innovation (INNO) has a direct influence on Loyalty of service users (LOYA) The influence coefficient is equal to $.41*(9.11)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, according to hypothesis 6. Service innovation has a direct and positive influence on service user loyalty.
- 7) Service innovation (INNO) has a direct influence on Deciding to use services (DECI) with a coefficient of influence equal to $.42*(11.97)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, according to hypothesis 7, service innovation has a direct positive influence on the decision to use services.
- 8) Trust (TRUS) has a direct influence on Loyalty of service users (LOYA) with an influence coefficient of $.71*(9.35)$ with statistical significance at the level of .05 is in accordance with hypothesis 8. Trust has a direct positive influence on user loyalty. serve
- 9) The decision to use the service (DECI) has a direct influence on Loyalty of service users (LOYA) The influence coefficient is equal to $.67*(10.53)$ with statistical significance at the .05 level, according to hypothesis 9. The decision to use services has a direct and positive influence on the loyalty of service users.

10) 13. Marketing mix (MARK), service innovation (INNO), trust (TRUS), service use decision (DECI), and being able to jointly predict Loyalty of service users (LOYA) was 58 percent.

The modified equation model can be shown as follows.

Figure 1 Modified equation model. (n=500)

Part 3- Creating a loyalty model for users of tutoring institutions in Phuket Province.

From quantitative and qualitative analysis, it was found that factors affecting user loyalty in tutoring institutions in Phuket province include image, marketing mix, and innovation in service. These factors directly influence trust with coefficients of 0.78, 0.54, and 0.48 respectively, all statistically significant at the 0.05 level, explaining 74% of the variance. Additionally, marketing mix variables and service innovation directly influence the decision to use services, with coefficients of 0.72 and 0.42 respectively, also significant at the 0.05 level, explaining 51% of the variance. Moreover, service innovation, trust, and decision to use services directly influence user loyalty, with coefficients of 0.31, 0.41, 0.71, and 0.67 respectively, significant at the 0.05 level, explaining 58% of the variance.

Based on these findings, the researcher developed a structural equation model named ISMTD-CLTP (Image, Service Innovation, Marketing Mix, Trust, Decision-making, Customer Loyalty of Tutoring Institutions in Phuket Province)

The first component of the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the image variable, denoted by I. This variable represents the perception of tutoring institutions, focusing on aspects such as location, teaching staff, and curriculum. Establishing and maintaining a good image is crucial for these institutions to succeed in their operations. Satisfied customers are likely to return and recommend the service to others, thereby enhancing trust among parents and students. A

positive image not only distinguishes the institution in the market but also instills pride in students and parents. Choosing a reputable institution boosts students' pride and motivation to learn

The second component in the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the service innovation variable, denoted as S. Service innovation plays a crucial role in the development of tutoring institutions by enabling them to adapt more effectively to evolving student and parent needs. It encompasses innovative teaching materials, advancements in learning environments, teaching effectiveness metrics, and the integration of new technologies for managing learning and curriculum development tailored to individual student needs. Technological and pedagogical innovations empower educators to enhance teaching efficacy and foster skill-focused learning, ensuring tutoring institutions thrive and expand over the long term

The third component in the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the marketing mix outcome variable, denoted as M. This variable is crucial for tutoring institutions as it aids in effectively attracting and retaining students. It also enhances competitiveness in the market. The marketing mix comprises various elements: Product, Price, Personnel, Marketing Promotion, Distribution Channel, Process, and Physical Characteristics. These elements help tutoring institutions adapt to changing market needs, such as modernizing curricula, improving teaching and learning methods through technology, and creating additional activities to develop students' skills. The marketing mix enables tutoring institutions to better understand and meet the needs of parents and students, thereby enhancing service delivery relevance and impacting user loyalty. Component 3, represented by M in the ISMTD-CLTP Model, influences user loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province

The fourth component in the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the trust variable, denoted by T. Trust is a crucial factor in fostering a strong relationship between tutoring institutes, parents, and students. When both the administration and teaching staff are trusted, parents and students feel confident that the tutoring institute can effectively manage their learning needs. Quality teaching coupled with this trust reassures parents that their children will be well cared for and have the opportunity to succeed academically. Trusted tutoring institutions often receive feedback and recommendations from satisfied parents and students, which is invaluable for continuous improvement and service development. When parents and students trust the institution, they are more likely to continue using its services, thereby fostering loyalty. This, in turn, helps tutoring institutes retain existing customers and attract new ones through positive word of mouth and shared good experiences. In summary, the trust variable (T) in the ISMTD-CLTP Model plays a pivotal role in influencing the loyalty of tutoring service users in Phuket Province.

The fifth component in the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the decision-making variable regarding the use of services, denoted as D. In this model, the decision to utilize tutoring services plays a crucial role in fostering loyalty among users of tutoring institutions in Phuket Province. These institutions primarily focus on preparing students for important exams such as university entrance exams or various competitive tests. The decision to engage with tutoring services typically begins with the expectation of a positive learning experience. If the institution meets

these expectations, students and parents are likely to be satisfied and inclined to return. Providing personalized attention and support enhances relationships with users, fostering loyalty. High-quality teaching that yields tangible results, such as improved exam scores or university admissions, reinforces users' confidence in their choice of institution. In conclusion, the decision-making variable (D) in the ISMTD-CLTP Model highlights the importance of service utilization in influencing user loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province.

The sixth component in the ISMTD-CLTP Model is the loyalty variable of users of tutoring institutions in Phuket Province, referred to as CLTP (Customer Loyalty of Tutoring Institutions in Phuket Province). Customer loyalty is a crucial concept in business management, particularly in tutoring institutes. The majority of service users are generally satisfied with the high-quality teaching and professional guidance provided, which helps students understand and succeed in their studies. Moreover, they are content with tutoring institutions that yield positive academic outcomes for students. The success of students in advancing to higher educational levels serves as a significant indicator of user satisfaction with the institution. When service users are satisfied and trust the institution, their decision to continue using the service influences their loyalty. Therefore, user loyalty to tutoring institutions plays a vital role in their operational success in Phuket Province. When all elements are combined, the Affecting Factor Model towards the loyalty of users of tutoring institutions in Phuket Province emphasizes the importance of the trust variable. Building trust in tutoring institutions requires comprehensive development in both administration and teaching. This component is crucial as parents and students seek assurance that the institution effectively aids in their students' skill and knowledge development. Next is the decision variable in service usage. This process involves service users considering and selecting services from various providers, comprising problem recognition, information search, evaluating options, and decision-making. Users often base their decisions on factors impacting satisfaction and perceived value. A tutoring institution that satisfies and effectively attracts customers influences their decision to use the service.

Customer loyalty is built when tutoring institutions meet their customers' needs, prompting them to return and recommend the service. The innovation variable in service provision can create engaging and satisfying learning experiences for users. Introducing innovations that add value and meet user needs enhances user loyalty. The marketing mix variables are essential tools for planning and executing marketing strategies in tutoring institution operations, efficiently meeting customer needs. Effective application of the marketing mix fosters satisfaction and loyalty among service users. Additionally, the image variable is crucial, as a positive public perception of a tutoring institution enhances customer trust and confidence. Establishing a favorable institution image involves prioritizing customer needs and satisfaction, employing highly skilled and experienced instructors who facilitate efficient knowledge transfer in a conducive learning environment. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of student outcomes, maintaining clean and attractive facilities, and offering modern amenities create an orderly and enjoyable learning atmosphere. Tailoring services to customer needs regarding location, teaching staff, and curriculum positively impacts tutoring institution operations.

CONCLUSION

This research delves into the dynamics influencing customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province, particularly within the context of competitive state university entrance examinations. It adopts a comprehensive approach, blending quantitative analysis with qualitative insights to uncover pivotal factors shaping student and parent perceptions.

Influential Factors: The study highlights that several key factors—image, marketing mix, service innovation, trust, and decision-making in service usage—play significant roles in shaping customer loyalty towards tutoring institutions in Phuket Province. These factors collectively contribute to the overall satisfaction and perceived value that students and parents associate with these institutions.

ISM TD-CLTP Model: Central to the research is the development of the ISM TD-CLTP Model (Image, Decision-making, Service Innovation, Trust, Marketing Mix, Customer Loyalty of Tutoring Institutions in Phuket Province). This model provides a structured framework for understanding and improving customer loyalty. It serves as a guide for tutoring institutions to strategically enhance their operations by focusing on these critical variables.

Qualitative Insights: Insights from qualitative research emphasize the imperative for tutoring institutions to embrace digital transformation. Adopting new technologies and innovations, enhancing communication channels, utilizing social networks for service delivery, and offering flexible learning modalities such as computer-based and online learning are highlighted as essential strategies. Moreover, maintaining consistently high service standards emerges as pivotal for nurturing sustained customer satisfaction and loyalty.

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed for tutoring institutions in Phuket Province: **Embrace Digital Transformation:** Accelerate the adoption of digital technologies to deliver tutoring services effectively. This includes integrating online platforms, leveraging educational software, and utilizing digital communication tools to engage with students and parents more efficiently. **Enhance Communication Channels:** Improve communication channels to ensure timely and transparent interaction with stakeholders. **Modernize communication methods** to cater to the preferences of digital-native students and parents, thereby fostering stronger relationships and trust. **Innovate Service Offerings:** Continuously innovate tutoring services to align with evolving educational needs and preferences. Introduce new teaching methodologies, interactive learning tools, and personalized learning experiences to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes.

Cultivate Trust and Satisfaction: Prioritize building trust through consistent delivery of high-quality education and services. Transparent practices, reliable tutoring sessions, and responsive customer support contribute significantly to fostering trust and satisfaction among students and parents. **Strategically Implement ISM TD-CLTP Model:** Utilize the ISM TD-CLTP Model as a strategic roadmap for decision-making and planning. Regularly evaluate and adjust strategies based on the model's insights to optimize customer loyalty and organizational effectiveness. **Policy Advocacy and Institutional Support:** Advocate for policies that support sustainable operations of tutoring institutions. Collaborate with educational authorities and stakeholders to

promote initiatives that enhance educational access, quality, and equity. These recommendations aim to empower tutoring institutions in Phuket Province to navigate the competitive landscape effectively, enhance customer satisfaction, and cultivate enduring loyalty among students and parents. By leveraging insights from the ISMTD-CLTP Model and embracing digital innovations, institutions can position themselves strategically for long-term success and impact in the educational sector.

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